

SIDE EFFECTS OF ANTIBIOTIC RESIDUES USED TO TREAT LIVESTOCK ON PUBLIC HEALTH

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Abstract: Antibiotics are used to treat microbial infections in farm animals and poultry farms, in addition to being used as growth promoters. The use of antibiotics is one of the future options that threaten human health. It was found that many antibiotics are incompletely absorbed and digested in the bodies of animals, leaving approximately 75% of their residues without any decomposition and thus excreted outside the body, resulting in high concentrations of residual antibiotics in the manure of farm animals.

The manure used to fertilize agricultural lands carries antibiotic-resistant bacteria or genes from dead bacteria that are easily transferred to the soil of agricultural lands. The presence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in the soil or resistance genes can be transmitted to humans through the skin, inhalation, or through plants. In addition, human consumption of meat and milk containing antibiotic residues is an additional source of transmission of bacterial resistance to antibiotics in humans. Accordingly, antibiotic residues in foods of animal origin have received great attention in recent years due to increasing concerns about food safety and public health. The continued heavy use of antibiotics while ignoring the accumulation of residues will lead to medical, economic and social challenges over time and will affect international trade, whether in the export and import of agricultural animals or their products such as meat and dairy.

Antibiotics

Antimicrobials are defined by the World Organisation for Animal Health as “natural, semi-synthetic or synthetic substances that exhibit antimicrobial activity by killing or inhibiting the growth of microorganisms” (Smith et al., 2015). This definition includes agents active against bacteria, viruses,

protozoa, and fungi. The term “antibiotic” is used in this study to describe antimicrobial agents that exhibit activity against bacteria.

There are several classes of antibiotics used in human and animal medicine, each representing a group of structurally related antibiotics. The penicillin, cephalosporin, carbapenem, and monobactam classes are grouped together as beta-lactam antibiotics (β -lactams) and represent the largest group of antibiotics. While other classes of antibiotics include aminoglycosides, tetracyclines, macrolides, quinolones, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, oxazolidinones, ansamycins, streptogramins, lipopeptides, and glycopeptides. Many antibiotics used in animal husbandry are from the same class of antibiotics used in human medicine (Marshall and Levy, 2011).

Use of antibiotics in humans

Antibiotics have been widely used to treat infections in humans. Penicillin, discovered in 1928, was one of the first antibiotics used to treat clinical infections in humans, and its use became widespread in 1941 (Shaban et al., 2014; Zaffiri et al., 2012).

Since the discovery of penicillin, additional antibiotics have been discovered and developed (Figure 2.1) due to the need to discover new antibiotics effective against resistant bacteria, especially after bacterial resistance to penicillin was documented shortly after its discovery (Finland et al., 1950). showed a clear difference in the sensitivity of penicillin in strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from hospital patients before 1946 to those found in later years, highlighting the emerging resistance to penicillin after its widespread use.

Inappropriate use of antibiotics in human medicine has contributed to the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. In bacterial populations, there are both susceptible and resistant bacteria. Resistant bacteria may be intrinsically resistant to antibiotics or may acquire resistance through mutations or horizontal gene transfer (HGT). Inappropriate use of antibiotics such as insufficient duration of treatment, low dosage, or selection of an antibiotic that is not suitable for the target bacteria creates selective pressure that enables resistant bacteria to survive. Thus, antibiotic-resistant bacteria proliferate and after a period of time are replaced by susceptible bacteria, which dominate the population. As shown in Figure 1.2 (Rosenblatt-Farrell, 2009)

Figure (1.2): Selective pressure and the development of antibiotic resistance. (A) The bacterial population consists of a mixture of susceptible and resistant bacteria; (B) Antibiotics provide selective pressure, eliminating susceptible bacteria while resistant bacteria survive; (C) Resistant bacteria dominate the population. Figure adapted from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Rosenblatt-Farrell, 2009).

Use of antibiotics in food animal production

The use of antibiotics in food-producing animals also contributes to the emergence of resistant bacteria. There is growing concern that resistant bacteria can be transmitted from animals to humans via the food chain.

The use of antibiotics in animal production can be divided into four different categories: therapeutic use to treat disease, prophylactic use to prevent disease development, therapeutic use to control disease, and growth promotion (Roughead et al., 2013). The United States, Canada, Australia, and Europe have different regulatory laws regarding the use of antibiotics in livestock and each has its own governing body responsible for regulating antibiotics. The antibiotics listed include those approved for growth promotion as well as those approved for therapeutic and prophylactic use as shown in Table 1.1 in the Appendix.

Concerns surrounding the use of antibiotics in food-producing animals were evident in 1969 following the publication of the Swann Report of the Joint Committee on the Use of Antibiotics in Animal Husbandry and Veterinary Medicine. This report made recommendations on the use of antibiotics in food animals and suggested that only antibiotics with little or no therapeutic application in either humans or animals should be allowed as growth promoters. Subsequently, it was recommended that the antibiotics chlortetracycline, penicillin, tylosin, and sulphonamides should not be used for growth promotion (Massé et al., 2014). The Swann Report was one of the first reports to promote changes in the use of antibiotics in food-producing animals. Some of these changes included the removal of antibiotics (such as penicillin) from animal feed in the United Kingdom, Australia, and several other countries, but this policy was not implemented in the United States (Barton, 2010). In the 1990s, the use of the glycopeptide growth promoter avoparcin was shown to be selective for vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* in cattle and poultry (Bager et al., 1997). Vancomycin is used as an alternative to ampicillin in patients with β -lactam allergy or to treat infections caused by penicillin-resistant pathogens, particularly methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and penicillin-resistant *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Arias and Murray, 2012). Widespread vancomycin resistance is a concern because it will reduce the effectiveness of this antibiotic, particularly for vancomycin-resistant enterococci, increasing treatment failure. Consequently, this prompted the European Union (EU) to ban the use of antibiotics to promote growth in livestock in 2006 (Prestinaci et al., 2015).

Fate of antibiotic residues used in livestock production:

Transfer of residual antibiotic in soil

Antibiotics are widely used in livestock farming for the purposes of treating infections and promoting growth, which account for more than 70% of global antibiotic consumption (Jechalke et al., 2014). Since many antibiotics are incompletely absorbed and digested in the animal body, approximately 75% of them are excreted without any degradation through urine (Chee-Sanford et al., 2009), resulting in high concentrations of residual antibiotics in animal manure (Fang et al., 2014; Qiao et al., 2018). When animal manure is used as organic fertilizer for soil, antibiotic residues will be transferred into the soil through several pathways, as shown in Figure 1.3.

Figure (1.3): Possible pathways for antibiotic transport in soil

The absorption of antibiotic residues in soil is one of the most common pathways where antibiotics interact with organic matter, clay, and mineral particles leading to adsorption, binding, and fixation of chemicals on soil particles. The strength of this interaction depends entirely on the soil solution (Kumar et al., 2005). The transport of antibiotics in the environment is related to their physicochemical properties where the transport of antibiotics in soil is mainly controlled by adsorption, soil solution pH, and ionic strength (Chen et al., 2012). In addition, the adsorption capacity of antibiotics also forms strong associations with colloids and dissolved organic matter that move to different soil layers (Ding et al., 2014). Figure 1.4

Figure (1.4): Adsorption of antibiotic residues in soil

Antibiotics such as Ciprofloxacin, Tetracycline, Doxycycline, and clindamycin are strongly adsorbed to the surface of aerobic solids. However, other antibiotics such as sulfamethazine and sulfamethoxazole are weakly adsorbed to the surface of these particles. The affinity of some antibiotics for surface adsorption may reduce their bioavailability (Wu et al., 2009) and result in low degradation rates (Dolliver et al., 2007). Antibiotics often have short half-lives (days to weeks), but at high concentrations, some antibiotics persist for months to years in the soil (Teeter and Meyerhoff, 2003). Antibiotic residues in soil are also adsorbed by some agricultural crops at different rates when they are grown in soils enriched with animal manure. Vegetables such as maize, potato and lettuce have the ability to absorb antibiotics as all plant leaves and potato tubers have shown the presence of sulfamethazine. Therefore, root crops (potato, carrot and radish) that have direct contact with soil are more susceptible to antibiotic contamination. Some of the staple foods enjoyed worldwide are mostly root vegetables, and the uncontrolled use of antibiotics in agriculture can jeopardize food security (Dolliver et al., 2007). In several studies conducted by (Hu et al. 2011), plants absorb antibiotics (clorotetracycline) from sandy loam and sandy loam soils when mixed with antibiotics containing raw pig manure. Thus, surface/groundwater and agricultural soils become reservoirs of antibiotics due to improper practices of fertilizing agricultural lands with animal manures (Hu et al., 2010) Figure 1.5.

Figure (1.5): Plants absorb accumulated antibiotics in soil

Transfer of residual antibiotic residues to dairy products

Antibiotics have been used globally by veterinarians for more than a decade in dairy farms to treat infectious diseases of dairy cows such as mastitis. These antibiotics include β -lactam (penicillin, Cephalosporins), macrolides, tetracycline, aminoglycosides, quinolones, and polymyxin (Fischer et al., 2011). Mastitis is a major social and economic problem in the dairy industry that causes a decrease in the quantity and quality of milk and dairy products (Reshi et al., 2015). In addition, antibiotic residues affect

the quality of raw milk used in the production of cheese and other fermented dairy products by inhibiting starter bacteria for fermentation by antibiotic residues, and it also reduces the production of desirable acids and flavors (Sachi et al., 2019).

The presence of antibiotics as residues in food products, especially milk, has certain harmful effects on public health from the pharmacological, toxicological, microbiological and immunological aspects, such as the transfer of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to humans, the development of allergies in some hypersensitive individuals (penicillin), increased risk of cancer (sulfamethazine, oxytetracycline) (Hou et al., 2015), nephropathy (gentamicin), bone marrow toxicity (chloramphenicol), and imbalances in the intestinal microflora (Back et al., 2020). Therefore, the presence of veterinary drug residues in food is an important issue related to food safety. These risks can be classified into two types: short-term direct risks and long-term indirect risks, according to the duration of exposure to the residues and the time of onset of health effects. Direct health risks include health effects resulting from drug excretion in milk, for example, beta-lactam antibiotics regardless of their low concentration in milk cause severe allergic reactions in sensitive individuals immediately after consumption, while chronic toxic effects occur with prolonged exposure to low levels of antibiotics which cause carcinogenesis, development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in treated animals and imbalance of normal human flora in the intestine (Priyanka et al., 2017). From this we conclude that once antibiotics are administered to the animal body, antibiotic residues are present in high or low concentrations in their products. Therefore, the use of antibiotics as growth promoters should be prohibited, and whenever they are used for therapeutic purposes, they should be used in appropriate doses and at the right time. Thus, the harmful effects of antibiotic residues can be minimized by following appropriate scientific guidelines and precautions.

Transfer of residual antibiotic to meat products

Over the past few decades, antibiotics have been widely used in animal husbandry, both for preventive and therapeutic purposes. It should be noted that one third of antibiotics used in Europe are for veterinary use, with poultry, pigs and cattle receiving the vast majority of antibiotics for therapeutic purposes.

In poultry, antibiotics are essential for the prevention and control of infectious diseases. They are also illegally used as nutritional supplements to stimulate animal growth and productivity, such as oxytetracycline, bacitracin, chlortetracycline, tylosin, neomycin, avoparcin and virginiamycin (Kantiani et al., 2010). Misuse and incorrect use of antibiotics carry the risk of their residues in edible tissues, which can cause toxins and allergies in hypersensitive consumers (Marazuela and Bogianni, 2009). In addition, human exposure to high levels of antibiotic residues from animal sources may exacerbate the immune response in immunocompromised individuals and negatively impact the gut microbiota (Normanno et al., 2007). Misuse of antibiotics may also lead to the development of resistant strains of bacteria, thereby reducing the efficacy of antibiotics used in animal treatment, leading to treatment failure in livestock, and negatively impacting animal health (Laxminarayan et al., 2013). The spread of antibiotic resistance is a major global concern due to concerns about the transfer of antibiotic resistance genes from animal microflora to human pathogens. Another risk is the transfer of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains through the food chain (Barton, 2000). The consumption of cattle and sheep meat is a particularly significant challenge in developing countries, while meat consumption is somewhat declining in industrialized countries. In recent years, to increase animal production, antibiotics such as sulfonamides, fluoroquinolone, tetracycline, and macrolides have been widely used in animal husbandry. In a study conducted by Zhang and his group, residues of these antibiotics were found in cattle muscles, sheep muscles, kidneys, and liver, which may pose a threat to human health (Zhang et al., 2021). As in poultry, antibiotics have the potential to contaminate foods of animal origin, especially meat, which causes many adverse health effects in humans, such as the development of multidrug-resistant microbial strains (Chang et al., 2015), allergies (Baynes et

al., 2016). In addition, bacterial resistance genes can be horizontally transferred from animal microbes to human microorganisms and human pathogenic bacteria (Marshall and Levy, 2011).

Mechanism of resistance of microbes to antibiotics

Resistance means the lack of response of microbes to antibiotics and is divided into natural resistance and acquired resistance.

1. Natural resistance

Some microbes are naturally resistant to some antibiotics because they do not have the metabolic pathway on which the mechanism of action of the antibiotic falls, such as the resistance of Gram-negative bacilli to penicillin or the resistance of tuberculosis bacilli to tetracycline (Nguyen et al., 2014).

2. Acquired resistance

It is the development of microbes to resistance by which they become unaffected by the antibiotic (Giedraitienė et al., 2011). The development of this type of resistance may occur through the following mechanisms:

Acquisition of resistance by genetic mutation

Where permanent changes occur in the genetic material of microorganisms and antibiotics may not be the cause of their occurrence, as any group contains a number of germs that have acquired a genetic mutation and which need a higher concentration of antibiotic to kill them and thus have the opportunity to survive and reproduce when the antibiotic eliminates the sensitive groups and over time resistant groups may replace the sensitive groups (Woodford and Ellington, 2007).

Acquisition of resistance by gene transfer

It may be called infectious resistance, as resistance can be transferred from resistant bacteria to sensitive bacteria in several ways, including:

➤ Conjugation

Where bridges are formed between resistant bacteria and sensitive bacteria, called sexual pilus, through which chromosomal or extrachromosomal (plasmid) DNA is transferred, meaning that the gene carrying the resistance (R-factor) is transferred from one bacterium to another. Conjugation may occur in the colon, where there is a diverse community of Gram-negative bacilli, where resistance may be transferred from non-pathogenic bacteria to pathogenic bacteria (Verraes et al., 2013).

Many resistances, such as salmonella typhoid resistance to chloramphenicol (Maka and Popowska, 2016), and E.Coli resistance to streptomycin (Kim et al., 2019), occur by this mechanism. Multiple resistance can also be transmitted by conjugation, so this mechanism represents the most important mechanisms of resistance transmission in the clinical aspect.

➤ Transduction

The transfer of resistance-carrying genes through bacteriophage is one of the methods of resistance transmission, where the R factor is taken by the bacteriophage and transferred to other bacteria, as some types of resistance to penicillin, erythromycin and chloramphenicol occur through this mechanism (Haaber et al., 2017).

➤ Transformation

In this type of resistance, the resistant bacteria release the DNA carrying the resistance genes into the medium, where it is transferred to other bacteria to become resistant to the antibiotic, such as the acquisition

of resistance to penicillin by *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and in general this mechanism is the least clinically important (Shousha et al., 2015).

➤ Cross resistance

It has been observed that the bacteria's possession of resistance to a specific antibiotic makes it resistant to other antibiotics that it had not previously recognized. This is often observed against antibiotics that are similar in their chemical composition or mechanism of action. For example, the resistance of the bacteria to one of the sulfenamides may make it resistant to all types of sulfenamides and acquire resistance to tetracycline, which makes the bacteria resistant to all types of tetracycline (Dopcea et al., 2020).

Cross resistance may also occur against antibiotics that do not have a chemical similarity between them, such as some bacteria that acquire resistance to Chloramphenicol, as it was observed that they are resistant to tetracycline (Puangseree et al., 2021).

1. There are other ways in which microbes can resist antibiotics, such as:
2. Secreting enzymes that digest the antibiotic, such as Beta-lactamase (Chika et al., 2017) lactamase
3. Changing the structure of their cell wall, which prevents the antibiotic from penetrating and destroying the bacteria. (Epanand et al., 2016)
4. Changing the target site on which the antibiotic works inside the bacterial cells; as each type of antibiotic usually targets a specific target inside those cells, the bacteria change their internal formation, and it becomes difficult to kill the bacteria or stop their reproduction (Radovic-Moreno et al., 2012).
5. The microbe changes its metabolism, which are the chemical reactions that occur in living organisms, including digestion and transporting materials to and between different cells in order to find new ways to continue living without being affected by antibiotics.

Methods for Detecting Antibiotic Residues

Antibiotic resistance is an international problem that poses a direct threat to global health, agriculture, and biosecurity. Since their concentrations in natural environments are not systematically tracked worldwide, this limits the international capacity to address the rise of antibiotic resistance at its sources. Therefore, it is necessary to develop methods to measure antibiotic concentrations optimally, in terms of sensitivity to low concentrations, cost, selectivity, and biosafety factors. Based on these criteria, methods for detecting antibiotic residues are classified into microbiological, physical and chemical, and immunological assays (Parthasarathy et al., 2018).

1. Microbiological assay

This is a classic method for determining whether certain antibiotics are present in a given sample at a limited sensitivity and concentration. Current assays rely on one of two methods. The first is disc diffusion, where discs are coated in the sample to be tested and then placed on the surface of a culture plate that has been cultured with bacteria; the presence of a halo around the disc indicates that the bacteria have been killed by the antibiotic in the disc. The sensitivity of this method can reach 30-80 ng/ml (Piech et al., 2016).

The second method is using specific bacteria with known sensitivity to antibiotics that have been engineered to show a color result. These color change reactions can be analyzed quantitatively using a spectrophotometer to determine the concentration of the antibiotic present in the sample. The sensitivity of this technique reaches 1 ng/ml. These two methods are suitable for detecting antibiotic residues in milk, specifically for detecting antibiotics belonging to the beta-lactam family (Kalunke et al., 2018).

2. Physical and chemical assay

Unlike microbiological assays, which are limited to bacterial susceptibility to antibiotics, physical and chemical assays target specific properties of the molecule such as size, charge, binding properties or reactivity to identify antibiotics in various samples (de la Huebra and Vincent, 2005).

Physical purification involves separating the antibiotic from other impurities in the sample to allow the isolation of the desired component through repeated fractionation. The final fraction of the purified antibiotic is analyzed using spectrophotometry (Zhang et al., 2013). The lower limit of detection for antibiotic residues is less than 25 ng/ml. The prepared sample can also be analyzed using several types of spectrometric assays such as tandem mass-spectrometry, which analyzes antibiotics present in the sample at levels less than 0.1 ng/ml. Liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC/MS) is also suitable for determining antibiotic concentrations in milk, serum, meat, soil, and water samples (Jha et al., 2017). For chemical assays, a microfluidic system was designed that allows the chemical reaction between antibiotics (aminoglycoside) and copper ions with a measurable chemiluminescent product carried on a chip. The minimum sensitivity of this method is less than 1 ng/ml (Gomes and Sales, 2015).

3. Immunoassays

Immunoassays are highly sensitive for detecting antibiotics in liquid or solid samples, depending on the specificity of the interactions between antibodies and the molecule to be detected. Immunoassays are usually colorimetric, fluorescent, or chemiluminescent, depending on the type of carrier. One of the immunological techniques used in this regard is the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), which is used to detect antibiotic residues in soil, food, and water samples. The minimum sensitivity of this technique is less than 1 ng/ml (Uttamchandani and Yao, 2017).

Approaches to reduce the use of antibiotics in food and animal production

Concerns about the association of antibiotic use in food animals with the development of antibiotic resistance in pathogens in animals and humans have led to attempts to reduce the use of antibiotics in animal production. The use of antibiotics is considered essential by many advocates to ensure animal health, growth, or production efficiency. When faced with the potential losses that can occur with the re-emergence of an active infection or disease in a particular herd, therapeutic measures must be applied. If the goal of animal production professionals is to reduce the inappropriate use of antibiotics in food animals, strategies must be implemented that offset the potential for increased severity and occurrence of animal infections (Da Costa et al., 2013; Weese et al., 2015). Strategies to reduce the extent of therapeutic antibiotic use fall into two categories: prevention of disease and infection, and documented diagnosis of the presence of the pathogen and selection of an effective and comprehensive antibiotic to eradicate the infection. Therefore, in order to reduce the repeated trial and error of antibiotics, the bacteria must be sensitive to the prescribed antibiotic and, most importantly, viral and bacterial diseases should not be confused (Pesavento and Murphy, 2014).

Conclusions and recommendations

The problem of antibiotic residues in animal products is not new. However, due to the globalization of food trade, we are constantly facing new challenges. It will be necessary to reduce the volumes of antimicrobials currently used by humans and livestock and to limit the use of broad-spectrum and critically important antimicrobials. Educational work on antimicrobial residues in animal products and the associated development of multi-resistant bacteria in developing countries should be intensified. This can only be reduced by increasing monitoring of the use of antibiotics in animal husbandry. The disposal of waste, sewage and manure containing antibiotics in this context should be prohibited. Alternatives to antibiotics, such as different vaccines, the use of phages and phage therapy, should be promoted. Further research

should also be conducted on the use of prebiotics and probiotics in animal feed and the use of traditional medicinal herbs to reduce the use of antibiotics in food animal husbandry.

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